

Grant Agreement No: 101004761

AIDAinnova

Advancement and Innovation for Detectors at Accelerators
Horizon 2020 Research Infrastructures project AIDAINNOVA

MILESTONE REPORT

MONITORING SOFTWARE DEVELOPED

MILESTONE: MS10

Document identifier:	AIDAinnova-MS10
Due date of milestone:	End of Month 30 (September 2023)
Report release date:	30/09/2023
Work package:	WP3: Test beam and DAQ infrastructure
Lead beneficiary:	UCL
Document status:	Final

Abstract:

Online monitoring tools have proven to be indispensable in test beam activities. As such, many test beam users implement their own monitoring tools tailored to their needs. The goal of work package 3 in the AIDAinnova project is to develop a common test beam and DAQ infrastructure. This encompasses the development of an online monitoring system which is implemented as part of the EUDAQ2 framework. In this document, we present the status of the development of such an online monitoring tool and demonstrate the ability to run the monitoring in different setups.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2023

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

The Advancement and Innovation for Detectors at Accelerators (AIDAinnova) project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement no. 101004761. AIDAinnova began in April 2021 and will run for 4 years.

Delivery Slip

	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	A. Loeschcke Centeno	UoS	31/07/2023
Edited by	L. Huth	DESY	06/08/2023
Reviewed by	L. Huth [Task coordinator] M. Wing [WP coordinator] Daniela Bortoletto	DESY UCL UOXF	05/09/2023
Approved by	Daniela Bortoletto	UOXF	30/09/2023

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION	4
2. CURRENT STATUS OF EUDAQ2 AND ITS MONITORING	5
2.1. EUDAQ2	5
2.2. EUDAQ2 STANDARD MONITOR	5
3. CORRYVRECKAN	6
4. CORRYMONITOR	7
4.1. WORKING PRINCIPLE	7
4.1.1. Detector Geometry	7
4.1.2. Corryvreckan Configuration File	7
4.1.3. DataCollectors to be Monitored	8
4.2. FEATURES	8
5. TESTS OF THE CORRYMONITOR	9
5.1. OFFLINE SETTING	9
5.1.1. EUDAQ2 Example	9
5.1.2. AHCAL	9
5.2. TEST BEAM SETTING	11
6. CONCLUSION	12
7. REFERENCES	13

Executive summary

This milestone describes the development of a monitoring software for the data acquisition control framework EUDAQ2. The document details how this software is implemented.

The current status of EUDAQ2 and the monitoring software is outlined in Section 2. The lack of desired functionality for the existing monitoring tool necessitates the development of a new monitoring software.

Since the commonly used test beam software “Corryvreckan“ is well suited to fulfil requirements set by the conveners of this task, it is used as a starting point for the development. In Section 3 Corryvreckan and its functionality are introduced.

Section 4 describes the process of implementing an online monitoring tool using Corryvreckan within EUDAQ2. It also explains the input required from the user to run the monitoring.

In Section 5 examples are given where this new monitoring tool has been tested, both in a lab setting and during a test beam.

1. INTRODUCTION

Test beams are the gold standard to test detectors under conditions close to the final experiment at the cost of requiring a high level of effort for seamless integration into the complex setup.

For the vast majority of test beam activities, having access to an online monitoring tool for data control is vital. It allows quick adaptation to unforeseen circumstances and to adjust data taking if necessary. Access to a robust online monitoring tool is therefore a large concern for test beam users.

EUDAQ2 [1] has been developed in the scope of AIDA-2020 [2] and is widely used in the test beam community. It is therefore imperative to further develop this software by implementing new functionality while keeping users' needs in mind.

While it is not uncommon for users to implement their own scripts for data monitoring, the EUDAQ2 software package aims to provide the users with a complete framework to control the data acquisition during the test beam, including an online monitoring tool. The current ROOT-based [3] online monitor offers only a minimal set of plots to check the data integrity. The aim of this task is to develop a new, flexible online monitoring tool, capable of overcoming the limitations of the current system and requiring minimal effort for the users to utilise.

2. CURRENT STATUS OF EUDAQ2 AND ITS MONITORING

2.1. EUDAQ2

EUDAQ2 is a data acquisition control framework, allowing the test beam user to centrally control the DAQ for all detectors connected to EUDAQ2. While originally developed to read data from high-precision test beam telescopes of the EUDET type, it has since been adapted to be used for any variety of test beam setups, due to a large interest and user base for other use cases.

Fig. 1 Architecture of the EUDAQ2 framework [1].

Its architecture, based on a modular approach, is depicted in Figure 1. The *RunControl* is the central instance with which data taking is controlled. It communicates via *Producers* with each detector, whose data are collected by the *DataCollector* and then written to disk. Optionally, data is forwarded to a monitor.

To use the EUDAQ2 framework at a test beam, the user has to implement their own *Producer*, which acts as an interface between the detector DAQ and EUDAQ2. If none of the default *DataCollectors* provided by EUDAQ2 fit the users' needs, they can also implement their custom *DataCollector* for data saving and a *DataConverter* to be able to read the EUDAQ2 standard output format. Similarly, the user can implement their own *Monitor*, should they require additional plots to the ones created by the default *Monitor*.

2.2. EUDAQ2 STANDARD MONITOR

The current monitoring module provided by EUDAQ2 is a ROOT-based monitor. One of the limitations of this *Monitor* is that it is only able to monitor data from a single *DataCollector*. As a consequence, the *Monitor* is not capable of any sort of event building and processing between various *DataCollectors*. Additionally, if the *DataCollector* whose output file is being monitored, does not take care of synchronising the data entries to events, there is no way for the *Monitor* to recover this information, as it processes entry by entry.

The goal for this task is therefore to revamp the monitoring system for EUDAQ2, fulfilling the following requirements:

- Monitoring of multiple DataCollectors
- Capable of flexible event building
- Track reconstruction of beam telescope data
- Preliminary analysis of device-under-test (DUT) data

Instead of updating the existing ROOT monitor in EUDAQ2 or starting from scratch, the widely used open-source test beam software *Corryvreckan* is used as a starting point, as it provides the functionality desired for the monitoring.

3. CORRYVRECKAN

Corryvreckan is developed as a reconstruction and analysis tool for test beam data [4]. Its modular structure allows it to be very flexible and configurable such that a large variety of users can benefit from the software, if needed by implementing custom modules tailored to their needs. While *Corryvreckan* was conceived to work particularly well with data from pixel sensors, the generic implementation of its modules allows for compatibility with many detector types.

There are a number of points which make the *Corryvreckan* software an ideal candidate to fulfil the role of an online monitoring tool at a test beam.

Event Building

Corryvreckan's event building can be configured extremely flexibly thanks to individual detector modules which are capable of defining an event based on the available information. Since at a test beam various prototypes with a wide range in requirements for experimental use are tested, *Corryvreckan* needs to be able to construct events from data taken by different readout modes. In particular, trigger-based, frame-based, and data-driven detectors are distinguished. A detailed description of possible event building strategies is given in [5].

Compatibility with EUDAQ2

Corryvreckan provides compatibility with EUDAQ2 via the `EventLoaderEUDAQ2` module. It allows data recorded by EUDAQ2 to be read and stored in the EUDAQ2 native file format into the *Corryvreckan* framework. The binary raw data is converted back to *Corryvreckan*-readable events. This natively supports all detectors, which have written their data in EUDAQ2 standard formats.

Tracking and Alignment

Modules required for the reconstruction of particle tracks and detector alignment are provided to the user.

OnlineMonitor

Corryvreckan provides an online monitoring tool that gives live feedback on the reconstruction progress and allows users to select any plot from any module to be displayed.

Fast and Minimal External Dependencies

By design, *Corryvreckan* has minimal external dependencies, to achieve a fast and lightweight framework. The use as online monitoring tool for EUDAQ2 envisioned by this task only requires three external packages: EIGEN3, for fast matrix calculations; EUDAQ2, required for the

EventLoaderEUDAQ2 module; and ROOT, required for histogramming and minimisation in the alignment and for the plots displayed by the OnlineMonitor module, which is already a requirement for the existing EUDAQ2 Monitor.

As established, *Corryvreckan* is capable of fulfilling most requirements set by the task. The main work that needs to be done is to integrate it into the EUDAQ2 framework such that everything can be centrally controlled from the EUDAQ2 RunControl.

4. CORRYMONITOR

This new approach for online monitoring with EUDAQ2 using *Corryvreckan* is developed under the name of *CorryMonitor*. The goal is to fully incorporate the monitoring into EUDAQ2, despite using an external software, such that the user is able to control every aspect of data taking from the EUDAQ2 RunControl instance.

4.1. WORKING PRINCIPLE

As the monitoring is done via a third-party software, there is no direct communication between EUDAQ2 and the monitoring. It is not possible to send EUDAQ2-style events directly into the *Corryvreckan* reconstruction chain for monitoring. Instead, the data is being read from disk. In this sense, the term “online monitoring” refers to the fact that the file that is still being written during data taking can be used as input for *Corryvreckan*, as multiple read pointers per file are possible.

The principle of the *CorryMonitor* module is to call *Corryvreckan* internally and pass it as much information as possible. The user should only need to provide the bare minimum information required for the monitoring to work. However, the desire for flexibility necessitates an increased amount of input by the user. Part of the development of *CorryMonitor* is the need to strike a balance between user input and flexibility.

The main sources of input required from the user are described below.

4.1.1. Detector Geometry

For its event building and tracking, *Corryvreckan* needs to know which sensors are placed at which positions in the setup. The user needs to provide some detector specific information about the geometry, such as position and orientation in the setup, number of “pixels”, and the pixel pitch for this detector. The “type” parameter is used to match the detectors involved in the monitoring with the DataCollectors responsible for the data saving. An example is shown on the left of Figure 2.

4.1.2. *Corryvreckan* Configuration File

In the *Corryvreckan* configuration file the reconstruction chain is defined. In this context “reconstruction chain” refers to the sequence of modules to be executed by *Corryvreckan*. A minimal working example can be seen in Figure 2 (right). In the first section global parameters for *Corryvreckan* can be defined, at minimum one path to the geometry file and one for the output.

The next section should be a module capable of defining an event in the *Corryvreckan* framework. Typically, this can be an *EventLoader* module, in the example given in Figure 2 this is done by the *Metronome* module. In this case the next module then reads the EUDAQ2 data. The chain is finished by the OnlineMonitor module.

```

[my_ex0_plane_0]
number_of_pixels = 16, 16
orientation = 0deg, 0deg, 0deg
orientation_mode = "xyz"
pixel_pitch = 55um, 55um
position = 0um, 0um, 0um
role = "dut", "reference"
time_resolution = -1ns
type = "ex0raw"

[my_ex1_plane_0]
number_of_pixels = 16, 16
orientation = 0deg, 0deg, 0deg
orientation_mode = "xyz"
pixel_pitch = 55um, 55um
position = 0um, 0um, 1000um
role = "dut"
time_resolution = -1ns
type = "ex1raw"

[Corryvreckan]
detectors_file = "corrygeo.geo"
detectors_file_updated = "corrygeo_updated.geo"
histogram_file = "corry_histo_file_example.root"

[Metronome]
triggers = 1
event_length = 100s

[EventLoaderEUDAQ2]
type = "Ex0Raw"
file_name = dc0_run416_230711153741.raw
eudaq_loglevel=INFO
use_as_monitor=1
buffer_depth=5
inclusive=1

[EventLoaderEUDAQ2]
type = "Ex1Raw"
file_name = dc1_run416_230711153741.raw
eudaq_loglevel=INFO
use_as_monitor=1
buffer_depth=5
inclusive=1

[OnlineMonitor]

```

Fig. 2 left: example of a Corryvreckan geometry file; right: example of a Corryvreckan configuration file.

4.1.3. DataCollectors to be Monitored

In the EUDAQ2 configuration file the user needs to specify which DataCollector to monitor, as they are modules which write the file to disk, which is used as input for the Monitor. The explicit file name does not need to be provided, instead the Monitor can get the file of interest from the file naming pattern stored in the DataCollector.

With an additional option specifying the corresponding event type that is being recorded with this DataCollector, the matching between the written files and the detectors is made. It is possible to specify the input file for each detector individually, therefore making it possible to monitor an arbitrary amount of DataCollectors. An example for the configuration section for CorryMonitor is given in Figure 3.

```

[Monitor.my_mon]
CORY_CONFIG_PATH=corryconfig.conf
CORY_OPTIONS=-v INFO
DATACOLLECTORS_TO_MONITOR = my_dc0, my_dc1
CORRESPONDING_EVENTLOADER_TYPES = Ex0raw, Ex1Raw

```

Fig. 3 Section for the Monitor in the EUDAQ2 configuration file.

4.2. FEATURES

Control

To be able to control the third party software from within EUDAQ2, the process ID of the Monitoring is stored upon start-up. This allows the RunControl to easily send command signals to *Corryvreckan*.

Arguments

Corryvreckan allows the user to adjust much of its behaviour via command line arguments. To maintain this level of control, the CorryMonitor allows the user to pass any options to *Corryvreckan* directly via the EUDAQ2 configuration file. The user can type any *Corryvreckan* flag-value-pair into the `CORRY_OPTIONS` setting (Figure 3) which are directly forwarded to the *Corryvreckan* call.

Changes to *Corryvreckan*

To further improve the user experience, some changes to the `EventLoaderEUDAQ2` in *Corryvreckan* had to be made. As *Corryvreckan* is meant to be used for offline data reconstruction and analysis, a natural feature of *Corryvreckan* is to close once the end of the file has been reached. In a test beam environment, however, it can occur that the end of file is reached before the run is over. In the configuration file for *Corryvreckan*, the user can now set a flag to prevent *Corryvreckan* from closing once the end of file is reached. Instead, *Corryvreckan* will wait for new events to be written to the file.

Multiple DataCollectors

One of the limitations of the default EUDAQ2 monitoring was its inability to monitor more than one DataCollector. The CorryMonitor can take multiple input files, each corresponding to one DataCollector. Upon the start of a new run the CorryMonitor automatically waits for all DataCollectors to create their data files and fetches the correct name without user interference.

5. TESTS OF THE CORRYMONITOR

5.1. OFFLINE SETTING

5.1.1. EUDAQ2 Example

To initially test the CorryMonitor functionality, the example Producer and DataCollector provided by EUDAQ2 were used. The randomised data allowed for quick testing of all the major functionality introduced to the monitoring. Indeed, apart from showing that the automatic file search succeeds, it permits the functionality to be tested with multiple DataCollectors. Figure 4 shows the monitoring for two data collectors with randomised data from the EUDAQ2 example.

5.1.2. AHCAL

After presenting the status of the monitor development in the AIDAInnova 2nd Annual Meeting, the AHCAL group from the Institute of Physics, Prague, offered to provide data for testing the monitoring functionality in an offline capacity [6]. Data taking was emulated by an EUDAQ2 producer which reads data from file and treats it as newly incoming data.

The CorryMonitor module was able to display the data from the files easily without adjustments in the implementation, confirming that indeed the monitoring works as generically as designed. Figure 5 shows the display of the monitoring with AHCAL data.

Fig. 4 Screenshot of running CorryMonitor with the example Producers provided by EUDAQ2.

Fig. 5 Monitoring of AHCAL prototype data in an offline setting.

However, the unique geometry of the AHCAL prototype with 38 layers also posed unexpected challenges to CorryMonitor [6].

One major issue was that all 38 layers were listed in the DUT section of the *Corryvreckan* window, taking up all the space and leaving none for the plots. This is depicted in Figure 6. The solution to this is to implement a scroll bar for the DUT section. This work is currently in progress. The screenshot in Figure 4 was taken with only four detector planes loaded into the geometry to prevent this issue.

Fig. 6 Screenshot of the monitoring window when loading all 38 layers of the AHCAL prototype into the geometry.

Another minor problem found during the testing with the AHCAL was that the Producer reading the data creates a lot of output to the console, overshadowing the monitoring output. To prevent this, the monitoring is now started from a new terminal window such that the print outs remain visible.

5.2. TEST BEAM SETTING

The monitoring was tested during a test beam campaign by the dual-readout calorimetry group for the IDEA detector concept [7]. While EUDAQ2 was not the main control system for the DAQ at this test beam, which would have been ideal testing conditions, there was a Producer available, which was able to read the data taken by the DAQ software and treat it as newly incoming data, similar to the AHCAL Producer. This, along with the corresponding DataConverter, was developed before the test beam for testing purposes of the monitoring software.

Thanks to extensive testing with offline data, the correct plotting of the data posed no issues. A photograph taken during the test beam, showing the monitoring of the calorimeter SiPMs is shown in Figure 7. The results from using CorryMonitor at the test beam are feeding directly into further development and will see implementation as part of the deliverable D3.4.

One important feature, which is still missing, is the ability to read in files from other PCs connected to the network, since EUDAQ2 allows data taking with multiple PCs in one network.

Fig. 7 Use of the monitoring software during a test beam of the dual-readout calorimeter group.

6. CONCLUSION

A versatile monitoring based on the *Corryvreckan* framework to build events with a high flexibility and monitor detectors of different readout styles has been developed. It has been successfully tested with offline data and at a test beam campaign. A few minor convenience features are currently being implemented to fully utilise *Corryvreckan* and EUDAQ2.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] Liu, Y., et al. (2019). *EUDAQ2—A flexible data acquisition software framework for common test beams*. *Journal of Instrumentation*, 14(10), P10033.
- [2] AIDA-2020, *Advanced European infrastructures for detectors at accelerators*, Available from: <https://aida2020.web.cern.ch/aida2020/> [Accessed 07 August 2023]
- [3] Brun, R., and Rademakers, F. (1997): ROOT—An object oriented data analysis framework. *Nuclear instruments and methods in physics research section A: accelerators, spectrometers, detectors and associated equipment*, 389(1-2), 81-86, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3895860>
- [4] Kröger, J., Spannagel, S., and Williams, M. (2019) *User manual for the Corryvreckan test beam data reconstruction framework*, <https://arxiv.org/abs/1912.00856>
- [5] Dannheim, D., et al. (2021). *Corryvreckan: a modular 4D track reconstruction and analysis software for test beam data*. *Journal of Instrumentation*, 16(03), P03008.
- [6] Sefkow, F., Simon, F., & CALICE Collaboration. (2019): A highly granular SiPM-on-tile calorimeter prototype. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series (Vol. 1162, No. 1, p. 012012)*. IOP Publishing, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-0221/11/06/p06013>
- [7] Giaz, A., et al. (2023): Test beam results of the fiber-sampling dual-readout calorimeter. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 1048, 167964. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2022.167964>

Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
AHCAL	Analogue hadronic calorimeter
DAQ	Data acquisition
DUT	Device-under-test
IDEA	Innovative detector for electron–positron accelerators